

Recommendation 14:

Using 'Crowdsourcing' to meet the public sector need 'Civil servants as a community of change'

Status quo:

Currently, crowdsourcing applied **in** the public sector refers to obtaining needed services, ideas, or content by soliciting contributions from a large group of people, especially an online community, rather than from employees or suppliers. To meet the need 'Civil servants as a community of change', crowdsourcing is to be applied **within** the public sector. This means government setting up a microtasking platform, not just for citizen engagement, but as a way to harness the knowledge and skills of its own workers across multiple departments and agencies.

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

- Working remotely from different locations poses a major security risk. Virtual team members could be accessing sensitive information from their homes or from public Wi-Fi networks

Non-technical challenges:

- *Training:* To broaden public employees' skills and the ability to handle multiple tasks and work on a variety of projects, learning should focus on social and collaborative processes in a distributed workplace
- *Processes:* Some changes to current human resource norms focusing on flexible work arrangements are needed
- *Organisation:* The way in which individual contributions are planned, assigned, coordinated and appraised must be carefully addressed

Civil servants as a community of change:

It is widely recognized that people, not organisations, drive innovation. This is even more true in the realm of public sector. Thus, it is necessary that the responsibility and the will to drive changes percolates down the hierarchy and become a responsibility at all levels: from top-level management to midlevel managers and front line staff. They must increase their ability to drive change by collaborating more and differently with each other and with end-users such as citizens, businesses and the third sector. Public sector innovation activities must become more embedded structurally, more strategic and more systematic. Sub needs include the need for a flexible public sector and the reflection that authorities need to be more open-minded. To further illustrate through the informants' voices: "Need of an organizational structure that is flexible and adaptable" and "The collaboration between different municipalities is still difficult".

Crowdsourcing:

*Describes the processes for sourcing a task or challenge to a broad, distributed set of contributors using the web and social collaboration techniques. Each person's contribution combines with those of others to achieve a cumulative result. Crowdsourcing applications typically include mechanisms to attract the desired participants, stimulate relevant contributions and select winning ideas or solutions.**

* Gartner IT Glossary – Crowdsourcing, <http://www.gartner.com/it-glossary/crowdsourcing/>